

Impact of Funding, Facilities, Provision and Management of Secondary Schools in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed funding and its impact on provision and management of facilities in secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study had two objectives and two hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 1532 comprising 25 principals, 1324 teachers, 175 SBMC officials and 10 MOE officials. A sample size of 306 respondents was used. A stratified sampling technique was used in which the respondents were classified into 4 strata based on their homogeneity. The instrument was structured on five points likert scale, validated and pilot tested with a good reliability established using Cronbach's Alpha. Descriptive and inferential statistics of ANOVA were employed for data analyses. The findings revealed that; adequate funding is essential for the effective provision and management of facilities in secondary schools, as it directly influences the quality and functionality of the learning environment. Therefore, the study made among other recommendations that; policymakers and educational administrators should ensure that funding is distributed equitably across schools specifically for the development and upgrading of critical infrastructures, develop and implement long-term infrastructure planning strategies that include regular assessments and updates, and explore alternative funding models such as public-private partnerships, grants, and philanthropic contributions to supplement government funding.

Keyword: funding, management, instructional facilities, Nigeria

Introduction

School is a complex social organization established for production of human capital. The school's input resources are human and non-human. These input resources are obtained, procured, produced or developed and utilized to produce the outputs. The operational input resources in the education sector are referred to as school facilities. The provision and proper management of these facilities have been found to be significantly related to school performance (UNESCO, 2022, World Bank, 2023, Ibrahim & Hassan, 2019, Li & Zhanq, 2022).

In spite of the importance of these resources in achieving educational goals, adequate attention has not been paid to their provision and management in Nigerian schools especially in rural communities. As elucidated by UNESCO (2019), inspectors' report over years has indicated that there is abundant evidence of a catalogue of inadequacies in the provision and judicious use of school buildings and materials for instructions in the country. Teaching and learning in a school can only take place if there is a provision of facilities, because the process involves learning experiences and interaction of learners with their environment (Oduwale, 2017, UNESCO 2019, World Bank, 2020).

It is government's responsibility to provide financial needs based on top priority as government can and ought to respond to the public secondary schools (Federal Ministry of Education, FMOE, 2019). Funding of education has drawn the attention of many educationists and scholars as education is seen as a major user of economic resources. Over time, effort has been made by the government to ensure improvement in the level of funding made available for the management of the secondary level of education. This is also the case in Katsina State where the government has relatively improved in the level of fund set aside for the development of the educational sector in the last few years (MOE, 2020). Various educational stakeholders have similarly highlighted that the quality of educational output is positively related to the quality of funding. Funding of secondary school education in Nigeria is the sole responsibility of Federal and State government. But in some cases, philanthropies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO's), Community people and other stakeholders where take part in

helping matters (Mohammed, Agboola and Isaac (2017). According to Bakwai and Yusuf (2016) as well as, the National School-Based Management Committee (NBMC, 2021) stated that, providing education for All is the responsibility of All.

However, funding of education generally and management of school facilities which comprises planning, organizing, staffing among others for the purpose of accomplishing a goal and development of education cannot be over-emphasized. All levels of education; primary, secondary and tertiary require sufficient level of funding in order to improve on the standard of education provided in the country. When funding is not provided in the right quantity and at the right time, it affects the education sector in so many ways. These concerns motivated the researchers to undertake this study with the hope that alternative ways may be recommended. Afolabi and Adeniji (2018) underscored the positive impact of funding for technology integration in Nigerian schools, improving instructional delivery and student learning outcomes.

The importance of adequate funding in education is key to any successful administration and management of secondary schools in Nigeria. No organization can carry out its function effectively without adequate financial resources at its disposal (Baker & Green, 2016). In Nigeria, secondary education derives its major fund from the annual allocation to the education sector. According to Ibrahim and Hassan, (2019) increased funding supports the development of facilities for arts education, including music rooms, art studios, and theatres. Additionally, funding helps in constructing sports fields, gymnasiums, and recreational facilities that promote physical activity and holistic development among students. Reports from the Nigerian Ministry of Education highlight government efforts to allocate funds for the construction and maintenance of arts and sports facilities in secondary schools, enriching students' educational experiences (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019).

The Theoretical framework was anchored on Ludwig von Bertalanffy's System theory (1954) which provides a framework for understanding complex systems, emphasizing interrelationships and interactions among components. According to this theory, the whole composed of interconnected parts that interact with each other and their environment. In the context of secondary school facilities, this means understanding that funding affects various interconnected aspects such as infrastructure maintenance, resource availability, and overall facility management. Systems theory distinguishes between open and closed systems. Secondary schools are open systems that interact with their environment .Funding impacts how these schools manage their facilities in response to external pressures and internal needs, influencing everything from building upkeep to educational outcomes. The theory also emphasizes feedback loops, where outputs of a system are fed back as inputs, influencing future outputs. In the case of school facilities, funding levels can influence the quality of infrastructure, which in turn affects student and teacher satisfaction, community perception, and even academic performance.

On review of related empirical studies two studies were reviewed Elujekwute (2021) examined the influence of funding on the management of secondary schools in south-east states of Nigeria. The Study investigated Influence of Funding on the Management of secondary schools in South-East States of Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised nine thousand four hundred (9,400) teachers from 220 grant-aided secondary schools. A sample of two hundred and ninety-six (296) teachers from twenty-five selected secondary schools was used for the study. A 15-item structured questionnaire by the researchers titled "Influence of Funding and Management of Secondary Schools Questionnaire (IFMSSQ)" was used for data collection. Descriptive statistics of Mean and Standard Deviations were used to answer the research questions while the Chi-square (χ^2) statistical tool was used to test the influence of funding on the management of human resource, on the provision of instructional materials and provision of schools' facilities, in secondary schools under the study area.

Another study reviewed was conducted by Amie, Ogan and Bikiya (2020) who researched on Educational Facilities Management for Public Secondary Schools Academic Improvement In the 21st Century. The study investigated strategies needed for the management of educational facilities for public secondary schools academic improvement in Rivers State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The descriptive research design was used. The population for the study comprise of 12 school managers and 240 school administrators totalling 252 respondents used for the study. Census sampling technique was used to draw the sample size. A self-designed questionnaire titled: "Management of Facilities for Public Senior Secondary School Improvement Questionnaire" (MFPSSSIQ)" was used to collect data from the respondents. The instrument was validated by three experts while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to achieve a reliability index of 0.90. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses.

The problem of funding is the most persistent and thorny issue militating against the school's capacity to maintain quality services in the country. Since the state government finds it difficult in recent times to provide resource and materials to

schools, it is obvious that if funds are inadequate. Education facilities are like the raw materials to an industry and thus are very essential to the whole processes involved in the educational enterprise. Educational development has come a long way, enrolment has risen tremendously while little funds is continuously being spent on the educational enterprise with the hope of improvement in terms of classrooms, computer facilities, libraries, laboratories, furniture, water and electricity supply among others. Whether provision of funds and management of facilities in secondary schools are crucial or not for creating conducive learning environments and ensuring educational quality are some of the gaps which this study addressed.

Objectives of the study:

1. Assess the impact of funding on provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State;
2. Assess the impact of funding on management of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant impact of funding on provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. There is no significant impact of funding on management of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Descriptive survey research design is a methodical approach used to gather and describe data about the characteristics, behaviours, or opinions of a population. This design is suitable for the study as it sought to adopt questionnaire to elicit respondents' opinion concerning impact of funding on provision and management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina State.

The target population of this study comprised of all secondary school principals, teachers, SBMC and Ministry of Education officials in Katsina Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. This Zone comprises of three Local Government Areas namely; Katsina, Kaita and Jibia. According to the Katsina State Ministry of Education (MOE, 2023) there are a total number of twenty-five (25) public secondary schools in the Zone with the population of 25 principals, one thousand three hundred and twenty-four (1324) teachers, one hundred and seventy-five (175) SBMC officials (such as the; Chairman, Vice chairman, Secretary, Treasurer, PRO, Auditor, and Patron) as well as (10) management staff of Katsina Education Quality Assurance (such as the Co-ordinator, Director Staff Matters, Director Quality Assurance, Director Exams, Director Sciences, Director Humanities, Director Languages, Director Sports, Director Guidance and Counselling, Director NYSC/N-power/S-power). Therefore, one thousand five hundred and thirty-four (1,534) target populations were drawn from the zone.

With the aid of Research Advisor (2006) recommendation table for determining sample size, a sample size of 306 respondents was used in this study. Stratified random sampling technique was used for the study. The respondents were first of all be classified into four strata depending on the nature of homogeneity with the first stratum constituting principals, second with teachers, third with SBMC officials and the fourth stratum with MOE officials. The study used all the 25 principals and 10 MOE officials and select 50 SBMC officials giving 85 respondents. The remaining 221 sample size was non-proportionally shared using simple percentage among teachers in the 25 public senior secondary schools in the Zone. Therefore, 25 principals, 50 SBMC officials, 221 public senior secondary school teachers and ten 10 MOE officials formed the study sample size from the total population.

The instrument for data collection was an adapted structured questionnaire tagged "Evaluation of the Provision and Maintenance of Facilities Questionnaire (EPMFQ)" designed by Sa'ad (2014). The instrument has two sections; the first section consists of the demographic information of the respondents such as; status, qualifications and year of experience, while the second section consists of twenty (20) items reflecting the research objectives. The instrument was structured on a four (4) points Likert scale of strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively.

The instrument was validated by two experts; an educational Management scholar and a Statistician from the Faculty of Education, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina. The validators who were experts in Test and Measurement

Psychology and Counselling made corrections on the instrument such as ambiguous or unclear statements, wrongly conceived ideas, missing information. Their corrections and comments were considered and adopted in the final draft of the instrument.

In order to establish the reliability index of the instrument, it was pilot tested in Government Secondary School Abukur in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The school was randomly selected out of the public secondary schools in the Zone. The basis for using the school is the fact that it is not part of the study area, hence cannot be used for the conduct of the main study. It was not be part of the sample. In the school, the researchers administered ten (10) copies of questionnaires to the principal, 5 teachers and 2 SBMC officials and 2 Ministry of Education officials in the Zone. The pilot testing tested the adequacy and suitability of the instrument in measuring appropriateness of the instrument.

The result of the pilot study was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha technique and the reliability index of 0.72 for the obtained and this indicated that the instrument is worth of the use for the conduct of the main study.

The permission for the conduct of the study was sought and secured for the conduct of the research. The researchers along with research assistants (the senior masters administration) of the sampled schools administered 306copies of the questionnaires to 25 principals, 221 public senior secondary school teachers, 50SBMC officials and ten (10) MOE Officials and were given adequate time for the filling of the questionnaires.

As for the data Analysis, Inferential statistics of ANOVA was adopted for testing the null formulated hypotheses at level of significance of 0.05. The data was processed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS version 23.0).

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant impact of funding on provision of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of ANOVA was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23.0). The detail of the result was presented in table 1.

Table 1: Summary of ANOVA of Difference in the Respondents' Opinion of Assessment of Funding and Its Impact on Provision of Facilities in Secondary Schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone

Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	231.487	3	77.163	.324	.632	Not Sig.
Within Groups	2186.710	282	77.818			
Total	2418.197	284				

The table 1 presents analysis of variance of difference in the respondents' opinion of assessment of funding and its impact on provision of facilities in secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone. The result indicated that the sum of square between the groups is 231.487; sum of square within the group is 2186.710. While, mean sum of square within group is 77.818 and between the groups is 77.163. The F-value recorded was .324 and P-value observed at 0.05 level of significance is .632. Therefore, P-value is greater than Alpha value. Since the observed P-value is greater than Alpha value, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Thus, this implies that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion of assessment of funding and its impact on provision of facilities in secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant impact of funding on management of infrastructural facilities in public secondary schools in secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone, Katsina State. In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of ANOVA was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23). The detail of the result was presented in table 2

Table 2: Summary of ANOVA of the Difference in the Respondents' Opinion of Assessment of Funding and Its Impact on Management of Infrastructural Facilities in Secondary Schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone

Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	206.234	3	68.7446	.9621	.392	Not Sig.
Within Groups	20104.072	281	71.5447			
Total	10310.306	284				

Result in table 2 presents analysis of variance of difference in the respondents' opinion of assessment of funding and its impact on Management of infrastructural facilities in Secondary Schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone. The table indicated that the sum of square between the groups is 206.234; sum of square within the group is 20104.072. While, mean sum of square within group is 71.547 and between the groups is 68.7446. The F-value recorded was .9621 and P-value observed at 0.05 level of significance is .392. Therefore, P-value is greater than Alpha value. Since the observed P-value is

greater than Alpha value, the null hypothesis is hereby retained (accepted). This implies that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion of assessment of funding and its impact on Management of infrastructural facilities in Secondary Schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of the study revealed that funding considerably enhances the management of secondary school infrastructure by providing the resources required for regular maintenance, timely repairs, and efficient renovations. This findings is in agreement with the assertion of Li and Zhang, (2022) and Oduwole, (2020) who earlier stated that provision of funding for secondary instructional facilities in schools promotes better management of schools which leads to better academic performance of students. The second finding of the study revealed that Adequate funding enables schools to create strong management systems to supervise the care of buildings, utilities, and other key infrastructure. provision of instructional materials such as modern classrooms, well-equipped laboratories, comprehensive libraries, and recreational areas that promotes better teaching and learning, protects student safety and comfort, which leads to improved academic achievement and general student well-being. This finding is in agreement with Bakwai and Yusuf, (2016). Also Ibrahim and Hassan (2019) who stated that maintenance of facilities in secondary schools have positive impact on Students' Academic Performance and that the support of Non-Governmental Organizations in the provision of instructional materials has schools to execute many activities, considering the fact that provision of education is the responsibility of all.

Conclusion

The study concluded that, adequate funding is essential for the effective provision and management of facilities in secondary schools, as it directly influences the quality and functionality of the learning environment and management of instructional facilities would enhance the quality of education This align with global resolution of the Sustainable Development Goal 4 target for inclusive education.

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, it was recommended that the:

1. Policymakers and educational administrators should ensure that funding is distributed equitably across schools specifically for the provision and management of infrastructures, develop and/ implement long-term infrastructure planning strategies. Such as by implementing public Private Partnerships by fourth Quarter of 2024 thereby targeting 20% facility upgrade
2. Policymakers and educational administrators should ensure that funding is dedicated to both the development and effective management of infrastructure facilities through implementation of data-driven approach to collect and analyze data on facility usage condition, and performance.

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